

Paper 2

INTERNSHIP AND EMERGING TRENDS AND TYPES WITH REFERENCE TO INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract

Internship may be defined as Academic Internship, Professional Internship and Research Internship. In United States and some other follower countries a typical Internship are deals with different opportunities. Professional Internship is another important types and most often this will be in the second or third year of the study period. The period can be from few weeks to two months to one full year. During this period, the candidate is expected to use the things they have learned in his/her course and put them into practice. This way the candidate gains work experience in their field of study. The gained experience will be helpful not only as his/her experience, but also for a permanent position in the same organization or any other organization. Academic Internship is practiced in the Higher Educational Institutes (HEIs) for the academic promotions. Similarly Research Internship is also offered to the academic candidates with focus on higher degree candidates. The Internship is increasing its popularity in the areas of Computing and Information Technology field. This paper is talks about different types of internship and its emerging types. Paper talks about the Information Technology focus in respect of internship, training etc.

Keywords: Information Technology, Internship, Employment, Job, OJT, Academic Internship, Research Internship

Introduction

Education is most important and valuable aspects of our life. Education is important and required in every sorts of our life. Traditionally education comes with formal mode of education and in-formal mode of education [1], [5], [11]. This in-formal mode of education also called as Non

formal mode of education. There are different ways in which education may be provided in this age. Information technology use is an important and most valuable in different context. Apart from traditional class room based education few more become popular in recent past viz. Distance Education, Online Education, Correspondences Education, E learning etc [2], [3]. For making education up-to-date and fruitful there are different kind of skill based components have been added such as—

- Training
- On Job Training
- Job Placement
- Internship etc.

It is worthy to note that, in professional fields and areas need of such skilling is much important and valuable. The fields are includes medicine, dentistry, pharmacy, law, education, architecture, engineering etc. Information Technology become an important applied field of study and applicable in different areas. Due to its applied nature different kind of Internship may be applied for its real life development and solid output [4], [6], [8].

Objective

The current research work is deals with following aim and objectives (such as)—

- To learn about the basics of formal and non-formal education in brief in Indian and International context.
- To learn about the basics of Training, On-Job Training (OJT) and their nature and characteristics.
- To find out about the basics of Internship with its types and nature in Indian and international context.
- To learn about the types of Internship in detailed and also to know about the need of these kind of Internship.
- To dig out the current status of Internship in a country like India.

Formal and Non Formal Education

Formal Education is most common and important as well traditional in nature. All the higher education settings normally offers education, training and skills with formal mode of education [7], [9]. In this mode of education different academic bodies are engaged in formal education systems such as—

- ✓ Schools
- ✓ Colleges
- ✓ Universities
- ✓ Institute of National Importance (INI)
- ✓ Research Center
- ✓ Autonomous Bodies etc

In this mode of education normal academic entities are include but not limited to the Class room teaching, use of assignments, use of projects, case studies etc. There are many other educational modes which include

- Distance Education
- Open Education
- Correspondence Education
- Online Education
- E Learning
- Blended Learning etc.

Training to Internship

Traineeship, Internships and similar aspects are most common in the professional fields which includes the areas of medicine, architecture different lab based science and engineering, commerce and business etc. The training and related affairs especially in the accounting and finance, technology, and advertising become common and important [8], [11]. A Traineeship may be defined as a term as well a position at the practical field where the candidate can learn the real life skills and simultaneously he/she can gather the experiences.

Research Traineeship is a combined activities can be deemed as a mixed mode and combined work of research activities and related matters and one can pursue the new skill sets or upgrade the skills for some one's research work and future job potentials. Research Trainee position is noticeable and importantly day by day this proliferation is increasing and importantly this trend becomes integral part of curriculum of many universities, internationally. In several countries the facet of Traineeship is an integrated part of the course, whereas in many universities courses are offered in the academic settings/institutes/universities and also in 'industries'. This type of industrial settings may be deemed as course-work of academic institutes but in with industrial context and by the professionals rather teachers/ professors [05], [10]. Here in this form of Research Traineeship some of the integrated aspects are—

- Pursuing the Course-Work in the industrial settings and offered by the real life practitioner, who are running academic venture.
- Lab-Work practices in the industrial settings and offered by the real life industrial practitioner and this is common with other Traineeship program.
- The research facet is an additional ingredients and thus it has very wider scope and here I also have been carry out R&D during the term apart from gaining Skills, Gathering of experiences etc.

Importantly, here the whole program is taught by the industry trainers etc. Hence the program of such model get much more priorities and acknowledged as more real and value added.

It is already been mention that the Traineeship or Internships, whatever may be classified as various ways and commonly the Traineeship may be defined as Professional Traineeship and Research Internship; though it can also classified as Academic Traineeship in some cases. We can notice various duration and a typical Traineeship lasts between 1 and 4 months but can be shorter or longer, depending on the organization's need, candidate's demand etc. The Traineeship differs from organization to organization, and country to country.

Internship and Emerging Types

A typical Traineeship is deals with following characteristics in United States and some other follower countries —

- *Academic Internship* is a kind of Internship which is helpful for the preparing manpower in the field of academic especially for the teaching and allied affairs. Internship is important and most valuable for making ready academic manpower. This kind of Internship may comes with credit or marks as well.
- *Professional Internship* is basically offered in the second or third year of the study period. The period can be from few weeks to two months to one full year. Here the candidate is expected to use the things they have learned in his/her course and put them into practice. Hence this is helpful for candidate who wants work experience in their field of study. Such type of experience will be helpful not only gaining his/her experience and even for a permanent position in the same organization or any other organization.
- *Research Internship* is another position where a Research Student or even fresher (in some cases) interested in research and allied field pursue the traineeship or internship. In this system the candidate is expected to improve, or the student can choose a topic within the

company themselves. The results of the research study basically need to provide and presented in the form of Research Report.

However the traineeship was combined with the 'skill sets' and 'research activities', thus the traineeship is also includes of all the features of a traditional Academic Traineeship.

Emerging Mode of Internship

Virtual Internship and Traineeship is another kind of industrial knowledge capsule (*In which the intern works remotely, and is not physically present at the job location. It helps in job experience without the conventional requirement and this is conducted via virtual means, such as phone, email, and web communication etc. The persons getting this kind of services may called as Virtual interns; here generally concerned persons work at their own pace*). This type of work helps in other assignment and similar affairs.

Internship and Current Need

Internship has its own value depending upon nature. There are different requirement of Internship; based on situation and case these may be applied. In generally Internship helps in professional practice. For example, a person studies architecture or civil engineering when pursued an internship will get real life exposure. Hence Internship also helps in getting experience [4], [11].

However, it is important to note that when an Internship is offered in the context of academic sorts (that is called Academic Internship) helps for creating skilled manpower to do teaching. Hence Teaching/ Academic Internship are also needed for preparing 21st century and updated manpower in the field.

Research is an important and most valuable asset for developing n organization, institutions, a territory and a nation as a whole. Hence for preparing a real life and advance manpower in this field, Research Internship is also important and required [03], [12].

This way, universities may started Internship as a part of the curriculum. Here Internship may be offered with credit or marks.

Masters Information Technology Program and Internship: International Context

Internationally universities are moved towards launching of internship program at the degree programs leading to Bachelors and Masters. In the Information Technology field Internship

become common in many universities internationally. Information Technology is a broad domain and consists with different branches viz.

- Networking Technology
- Web Technology
- Database Technology
- Multimedia Technology
- Software Technology
- Security and Emerging Technologies etc.

In all this emerging areas Internship are essential and as a result many universities have started initiative to introduce this. The table: 1 depicted list of few universities started Internship program either by mandatory or optional case.

Table: 1-Masters Information Technology program with Internship opportunities

Program	Universities	Remarks
Master of Information Technology	The University of Auckland	60 Points Internship Must
Master of Information Technology	Macquarie University	Internship offered as Option
Master of Information Technology (Computing & Networking)	James Cook University	Internship offered as Option
Master of Information Technology	Valparaiso University	Internship or Research Project is offered
Master of Information Technology	RMIT University	Internship is offered
MS Information Systems & Operation Research	University of Florida	Internship is must
MS (Information Technology and Management)	The University of Texas at Dallas	Internship is must

MS (Information Technology)	Purdue University	Internship is optional
MS (Information Technology)	The University of New Hampshire	Internship is must
MSc Information Systems	University of West London	Internship is must
Master of Information Technology	Eastern Institute of Technology	Internship is must
MS (Information Technology)	Loyola University, Chicago	Internship is optional

Internship and India

India is a large nation and developing in every sorts. The development of education sector is noticeable. India holds more than forty thousand Higher Educational Institutes (HEIs) and among these only in professionals subjects internship become mandatory viz. Medicine, Dentistry, Pharmacy, Optometry, Nursing and Allied Medical Sciences. In Engineering Internship was not mandatory up to 2017. But recently AICTE taken decision to do Internship as must for earning Bachelors Degree in the field of Engineering and Technology. Under this scheme 600-700 Hours may be consider for Internship. So this is an important and valuable move by the AICTE for introducing Internship. Though all these are professional internship so, other kind of internship such as Research Internship or Academic/ Teaching Internship may also started in future.

Similar to Engineering and Technology, in Education stream also for earning a B.Ed. degree Internship become common and started in recent past. Though till 2015 there was no such strong concept except a short term practice teaching.

Conclusion

This way, universities and similar kind of educational institutions may grab the potentialities of Internship into the program and course. It is worthy to note that universities like India may started Internship as part of the curriculum either by optional or mandatory basis. The Internship may be started in the program/ full-fledged degree or even into the particular course or paper. India hold 40000+ Higher Educational Institutes (HEIs) and there are numerous academic programs and all of these program may be rejuvenated by introducing new mode of education,

assignment, teaching-learning activities. Internship may be started in the program either in-general one i.e. Professional Internship or may be more recent Academic Internship or Research Internship. Though combination of all are possible in case to case basis.

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